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FAST DISSOLVING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS: A NOVEL APPROACH FOR ENHANCED THERAPEUTIC ACTION

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ABSTRACT

Among the increasing advancement in technology different novel drug delivery systems are introduced. In those fast dissolving drug delivery system has played an important role in providing the patient satisfaction and convenience. Oral route of drug administration is the most important method for systemic effect. Among the pharmaceutical dosage form, the conventional tablet seems to be most popular because of its ease of transportation and comparatively low manufacturing cost. It is generally done for the tablets which perform fast pass metabolism. These dosage forms disintegrate fast in the oral cavity and increase the bioavailability. Fast dissolving dosage forms are also called mouth dissolving dosage forms or super disintegrants. They are of tablet type and film type. It also has some important ideal characters such as easy portability, easy manufacturing, and accurate dosing. These dosage forms not only solve the purpose of oral route it also helps in disintegration of drugs in oral cavity within sixty seconds without swallowing or chewing. It can be easily taken orally without the help of water. It is helpful in providing patient compliance for people especially pediatric, disabled, patients having psychological problems and geriatric patients.

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INTRODUCTION

These fast dissolving drug delivery systems are the advanced technology of novel drug delivery system. Even though oral route of administration has several benefits it has some issues also. Different varieties of dosage forms are available in the market such as tablets, syrups, suspensions, suppositories, injections, transdermal and patches. Their route of administration is different from one another. These different dosage forms have different advantages. Oral route of drug administration have a great acceptableness for about 50-60% when compared to other dosage forms. Solid dosage forms are popular because it has some of the ideal characters like easy means of administration, accurate dosage, easy for self-medication, medication with no pain and mostly it provides the compliance of the patient. Sometimes it creates difficulty in swallowing oral dosage forms such as tablet when the accessibility of water not there. It also seems to be problematic in the case of people suffering with motion sickness (kinetosis) and sudden episodes of coughing during the common cold, allergic condition and bronchitis. [1, 2]

The other common problems observed were tablet size, surface form and taste. This will creates difficulty in swallowing tablets especially for geriatric and pediatric patients, as well as travelling patients who may not have ready access to water. This dosage forms also creates problem in young individuals and in schizophrenic patients which lead to dissatisfaction of patient compliance. The oral route of drug administration, some of the problems of gastro intestinal tract is also seen. Fast dissolving dosage forms were first developed in the year late 1970s as alternative drugs to the drugs of oral route of dosage forms in order to satisfy the pediatric and geriatric patient. There was survey conducted for the people who all are taking oral dosage form for administration. It was found that 26% of 1576 patients are facing difficulty and inconvenience in swallowing tablets. United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) stated that Fast Dissolving Tablets (FDTs) are the tablets which contain the active ingredient which will disintegrate within seconds when they are placed in oral cavity. [1, 2, 3]

Fast dissolving tablets:

These are also known as mouth-dissolving tablets, repimelts, porous tablets, quick dissolving tablets. These tablets have the capability to dissolve or disintegrate in the oral cavity without the presence of water. Most of these dosage forms include active ingredients and other excipients also added to mask the unpleasant taste of active ingredient. When these are entered in to oral cavity they dissolve or disintegrate within seconds and they mix with saliva and get absorbed in oral cavity or some of they get absorbed even in pharynx and esophagus. Faster they dissolve, faster they absorb and they show quick onset of action. Their bioavailability is also high. [4]

Fast dissolving Films:

These are the small polymeric strips rapidly dissolve within a fraction of seconds when placed on the mucosal surface in order to release the active ingredients without the use of water. These are also similar to that of fast dissolving tablets which will dissolve and disintegrate in oral cavity within seconds and get absorbed in the oral cavity. There are several advantages for these fast dissolving films as they are more stable, more durable and quicker than conventional dosage forms with patient compliance. It is used as local anesthetic agent and also used in treatment of oral ulcers. Handling of the drug and its transportability is also better than other drugs. And there is no risk of choking in these drugs. [4].

Criteria for selection of excipients used in fast dissolving dosage forms:

- The excipients should not show the individual effect.
- The excipients should have the ability to disintegrate quickly.
- It should not react with other excipients and the active drug ingredient.
- Care must be taken while selecting a binder (either a single or the combination of binders) which affects the integrity and stability factors.
- The melting point of the excipients used should be in the range of 30-35 °C.
- The excipients should not affect the efficacy and organoleptic properties of the drug.
- Different binders can be used - Liquid or solid or semisolid.[5]

Salient features of fast dissolving dosage forms:

An easy administration of drug can be carried out to the patients who are bedridden, pediatric patients, patients who became old and cannot swallow and also for psychiatric patients.

- It can be administered even in the absence of water which survives the patients many times when water is not accessible to them.
- Dissolution and absorption of these dosage forms are quick and rapid so they show immediate onset of action.
- As the absorption of the drug is taking place in mouth, pharynx, esophagus and sometimes in stomach when saliva flows in to it, the bioavailability of the drug is also high.
- Pre-gastric absorption will increase the bioavailability of the drug and by the reduction of unwanted effects its clinical performance is also increased.
- By improving the good mouth feeling property the perception of medication is a better drug especially used for pediatric patients.
- It has a better safety measure when compared to conventional oral route of administration as it avoids the physical obstruction of choking or suffocation.
- It is also beneficial in providing new business opportunity like product differentiation, product promotion, patient extensions and life cycle-management.
- It plays a beneficial role during the conditions of motion sickness, allergic conditions, coughing where immediate onset of action is required.
- It also increases the bioavailability of the drug even in the cases of insoluble or hydrophobic drugs as it has higher disintegration and dissolution rates.
- It also has a greater stability factor for storage conditions of longer periods of time [6, 7].

Ideal characteristics:

- The active pharmaceutical ingredient which is incorporated should have lower dose of lesser than 40mg.
- The drug should possess a pleasant taste.
- The drug should be easy to dissolve and disintegrate.
- The drug should have both solubility and stability properties in water and saliva.
- It should be partially unionized form in the buccal cavity.
- It can also be able to permeate in to oral mucosal cavity [8].

Benefits of fast dissolving films over fast dissolving tablets:

- Fast dissolving films will provide larger surface area for disintegration.
- They have no friability loss.
- Less expenditure will take place in processing and manufacture when compared to fast dissolving tablets.
- Fear of choking is not there.
- Time consumption is also less.
- It is more elegant.
- It is more economical [8, 9].

Biopharmaceutical considerations of fast dissolving dosage forms:

Before designing a new pharmaceutical dosage form some biopharmaceutical factors are to be considered. Fast dissolving dosage forms will easily absorb in the oral cavity, pharynx and esophagus. Some of the factors like age, nature of oral cavity, blood flow to the oral cavity are to be considered. Some other factors like permeability, perfusion rate, binding nature and drug interaction are to be considered to know the distribution of drug among the body. Pharmacodynamic activity of the drug depends on several factors such as age, sex, health condition of the patient [9, 10].

Methods for preparation of fast dissolving dosage forms:

There are various methods and techniques present for the preparation of fast dissolving dosage forms. Each method or technique of preparation has its own importance over the other.

These methods of preparation affect the various factors of dosage forms. Some of the factors are-

- Mechanical strength of the dosage forms.
- Organoleptic properties of the dosage forms.
- Dissolution and disintegration rate of dosage form.
- Good mouth feel.
- Rate of absorption of drug in saliva.
- Bioavailability of drug [11].

Different methods of preparations as follows: [12-22]

- Compaction method.
- Granulation method.
- Lyophilization.
- Tablet molding process.
- Nanotization.
- Spray drying process.
- Cotton candy process.
- Sublimation method.
- Mass extrusion method.

Compaction:

It is a conventional process in which fast dissolving tablets are prepared by using tablet press. The compression is done to the ingredients to get fine tablets. Tablets strength is based on the compressibility of the tablet. It is very conventional process as it takes less time and expenditure for manufacturing.

Granulation:

It is of two types, one is dry granulation and other is wet granulation. In this process a hydrophilic waxy binder super-polystearate, PEG-6-stearate is used. Super-polystearate not only acts as binder and increase physical resistance of tablet but also helps the disintegration of tablet. Due to that the fast dissolving tablets melts in the mouth and solubilizes rapidly leaving no residue.

Lyophilization:

This method is also known as freeze drying method. In this method the heat sensitive drugs and biologicals are passed at low temperatures which provide under suitable conditions that allows removal of water by sublimation. Drugs are dissolved or dispersed in aqueous solution of carrier and then it is transferred and subjected to nitrogen flush to freeze. Lyophilization results in the preparations which are highly porous and have a specific surface area. They have high dissolution rate which can be absorb easily and their bioavailability is also high. Some of the disadvantages with this method of preparation are that it is high of cost, it is time consuming process, inappropriate packing of this dosage forms and it also found that there are some stability issues also. Lyophilization mechanism is explained in fig.-1.

Fig.-1: Lyophilization mechanism.

Moulding process:

A Water soluble ingredient with hydro-alcoholic solvents is used. Then moulding is done by different heating techniques and in some pressure conditions. The pressure applied should be lower than conventional tablet compression. This process is explained in fig.-2 given below.

Compression Cycle Of Rotary Presses

62

Fig.-2: Representation of moulding process.**Nanotization:**

This technology involves reduction of particle size of the drug to nano size by milling process is done. Generally a proprietary wet milling technique is used for this. Then the nano crystals of the drug are stabilized for agglomeration by surface adsorption on selected stabilizers, and then they are incorporated in fast dissolving tablets. This method is used for poorly water soluble drugs. This have several advantages like less cost of manufacturing, high dissolution and high disintegration rate. Absorption is also high there by it improves the bioavailability.

Spray method:

In this technique hydrolysed and non hydrolysed agents are added as supporting agents. Then mannitol is added as bulking agent. Sodiumstarchglycollate or crosscarmellose used as disintegrating agent.

For enhancing the rate of dissolution or disintegration an acidic material or alkali material is added. There is an important characteristics in this method, it gives rapid dissolution (within 20 seconds) when it gets in contact with aqueous medium. This method is explained in fig.-3 given below.

Fig.-3: Schematic representation of spray process.**Cotton candy process:**

In this process spinning mechanism is utilized to produce floss-like crystalline structure, which mimics cotton candy. In the Cotton candy process involves formation of matrix of polysaccharides or saccharides by simultaneous action of flash-melting and spinning. The matrix formed is partially re-crystallized to have improved flow properties and compressibility. This candy floss matrix is then milled and blended with active ingredients and excipients and subsequently.

Mass extrusion:

This process involves softening the active blend using the solvent mixture of water soluble polyethylene glycol, methanol. Expulsion of softened mass is done through the extruder or syringe to get a cylindrical shape of the product into even segments using heated blade to form tablets. The dried product can be used to unmask the bitter tasting drugs and by coating them.

Sublimation:

Sublimation is the process used to produce fast dissolving tablets with high porosity. A porous matrix is obtained by compressing the volatile ingredients along with other excipients into tablets. Then they are finally sublimated. Generally inert solid ingredients having high volatility (e.g. ammonium bicarbonate, benzoic acid, camphor, hexamethylenetetramine, naphthalene, phthalic anhydride, urea and urethane) have been used for this purpose. Solvents such as cyclohexane and benzene were also used for improving the porosity. Sublimation is explained in fig.-4 given below.

Fig.-4: Flowchart for sublimation process.

Patented Technologies of Fast Dissolving Dosage Forms:

There are some other patented technologies also which are used in preparation of fast dissolving dosage forms [23-27].

Zydis technology:

- In this technology lyophilization process is carried out.
- In this technology rapid dissolution is carried
- It is self-preserving and also increases bioavailability.
- It is very expensive manufacturing process.
- At higher temperatures and humidity it exhibits poor stability.

Orasolv technology:

- In this process the lyophilization process is involved.
- In this process taste-masking of the drug is increased.
- A quick dissolution rate is observed in this process.
- In this process the product obtained mechanical strength is poor.

Durasolv technology:

- In this molding process is done.
- These have higher mechanical strength than compared to Orasolv technology.
- It has good rigidity.
- It is inappropriate when larger dose is considered.

Flash-dose technology:

- In this cotton candy process is involved.
- It has high surface area for dissolution.
- It requires a high temperature to melt the matrix can limit the use of heat-sensitive drugs, sensitive to moisture and humidity.

Flash-tab technology:

- In this technology tablets were prepared by using an active ingredient in the form of micro crystals.
- Microgranules may be prepared by using the conventional techniques like coacervation, microencapsulation, and extrusion-spheronisation. All the processes utilized conventional tableting technology.

Wow-tab technology:

- In this process, there are a low mouldability saccharides and high mouldability saccharides.
- Combination of both the high and low mouldability saccharides is done to obtain a rapidly melting strong tablet.
- The active ingredient is mixed with a low mouldability saccharine and granulated with a high mouldability saccharide and then it is compressed into tablet. In this technology adequate dissolution rate and hardness is observed.

Oraquick technique:

- This technique is used for the fast production and efficient production of drugs.
- It is appropriate for heat-sensitive drugs.

Ziplet Technique:

- It has good mechanical strength. Satisfactory properties can be obtained at high dose (450 mg) and high weight (850 mg).
- Its disadvantage is that when the soluble component dissolves, rate of water diffusion in to tablet is decreased because of formation of viscous concentrated solution.

Manufacturing:

Different processes combination is involved in the manufacture of fast dissolving dosage forms [28-31].

Solvent casting method:

In this method two steps are involved. In the first step, water soluble polymers are dissolved in water and in the second step; the drug along with other excipients is dissolved in suitable solvent. Then both the solutions are mixed and stirred until a homogenous solution is formed. Finally it is casted in to the petri plate, dried and cut in to uniform dimensions. Care must be taken to prevent the moisture content.

Semi solid casting:

In this method a solution of water-soluble film forming polymer is prepared. Then add a solution of acid insoluble polymer (e.g. cellulose acetate butyrate, cellulose acetate phthalate), which was prepared by ammonium or sodium hydroxide to this solution. Then required amount of plasticizer is added to the solution then it forms a gel mass. This gel mass is casted in to the films or ribbons using heat controlled drums. The thickness of the film should be about 0.015-0.05 inches. The ratio of the acid insoluble polymer to film forming polymer should be 1:4.

Hot melt extraction:

In hot melt extrusion method at first the drug is mixed with carriers in solid form. Then the mixture is melted by using extruded by the heaters. Finally the melt is shaped in to films by the dies. There are some advantages for hot melt extrusion.

- These are fewer in operational units.
- These have better content uniformity.
- It is an anhydrous process.

Solid dispersion extrusion:

In this method first immiscible components are extruded with drug. By that solid dispersions are prepared. Then the solid dispersions are shaped in to films with the help of dies.

Rolling method:

In rolling method a solution or suspension containing drug is subjected to roller. The solvent is mainly water and mixture of water and alcohol. Then the film is dried on the rollers and it is made to cut in to desired shapes and sizes.

Formulation:

There are different excipients used along with the active ingredients in the formulation of fast dissolving dosage forms. They are as follows

Nature of the film former:

Film formed should be tough enough so that it should not damage while handling or during the transportation. Type of polymer and the amount present in it is responsible for the robustness of the film. Some of the examples of the film formers are hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, hydroxy propyl cellulose, polyvenyl alcohol, sodium alginate, pullunan etc. [32-34].

Stabilizing and thickening agents:

Viscosity and consistency factors depend on this stabilizing and thickening agents. By using these agents viscosity and consistency is increased. Some of the examples of stabilizing and thickening factors are natural gum such as xanthum gum, locust bean gum and cellulosic derivatives etc. [34].

Plasticizers:

Plasticizers impart strength, flexibility and gloss to the film. For obtaining good and elegant film plasticizers are added along with the film formers. Some of the plasticizers are phthalate esters, phosphate esters, esters of oleate etc. [35].

Super disintegrants:

There are different super disintegrants used as excipients in fast dissolving dosage forms. These are the disintegrants which help the active ingredient of the drug to disintegrate. There are different super disintegrants given below- crosspovidone, microcrystalline cellulose, sodium starch glycollate, sodium carboxy methyl cellulose, pregelatinized starch, calcium carboxy methyl cellulose, and modified corn starch. Sodium starch glycollate has good flowability than crosscarmellose sodium. Cross povidone is fibrous nature and highly compactable [36, 37].

Flavors:

Flavors are the pharmaceutical excipients which are very much essential for fast dissolving dosage forms. These flavours add a conventional taste to the drug. So that it can also mask the bitterness of the drug. By the addition of these flavours we can fulfill the compliance of the patient. Some of the flavours are listed below which can be used as an excipients in Fast dissolving drugs. Examples are as follows- Peppermint flavour, cooling flavor, flavor oils and flavoring aromatic oil, peppermint oil, clove oil, bay oil, anise oil, eucalyptus oil thyme oil, oil of bitter almonds. Flavoring agents include, vanilla, citrus oils, fruit essences. [38].

Sweeteners:

Sweeteners are also one of the excipients used in the fast dissolving dosage forms. These sweeteners are added to the drug to mask the unpleasant taste of the drug. Some of the examples used in these fast dissolving drugs are aspartame, sugars derivatives. [39].

Fillers:

Fillers are also one of the excipients used in the manufacture of fast dissolving dosage forms. These fillers are helpful in improving the cohesion and also to adjust the weight of the tablet as per the dye capacity.

Examples are as follows- Directly compressible spray dried mannitol, orbital, xylitol, calciumcarbonate, pre-gelatinized starch, magnesium trisilicate, aluminium hydroxide.

Surface active agents:

Surface active agents are the excipients used in fast dissolving dosage forms, which helps in increasing the surface area of the drug. Some of the examples are- sodium doecyl sulfate, sodium lauryl sulfate, polyoxyethylene sorbitan fatty acid esters (Tweens), sorbitan fatty acid esters (Spans), polyoxyethylene stearates.

Lubricants:

These are the substances added as excipients to the fast dissolving dosage forms to avoid friction, sticking and picking of the tablet. These lubricants enhance the flow properties of the drug.

Some of the examples of the lubricants are stearic acid, magnesium stearate, zinc stearate, calcium stearate, talc, polyethylene glycol, liquid paraffin, magnesium lauryl sulfate, colloidal silicon dioxide.

Evaluation of Fast dissolving dosage forms: [39-43]**Size and shape:**

The size and shape of the tablet is by observing its physical appearance. Then the tablet size is measured in all the dimensions by taking the length, breadth and height. In this way size and shape is observed and evaluated by comparing with standard one.

Test for thickness:

Tablet thickness is an important evaluation test. This test has an important characteristic in reproducing appearance and also in counting by using filling equipment. In this test some filling equipment utilizes the uniform thickness of the tablet. And for the films dial gauge tester is used where thickness at different points is measured and average is calculated.

Uniformity of weight:

For obtaining the uniformity of weight batch of tablets were taken and their individual weights are taken and their average is calculated. In this way the uniform weight is obtained for that batch. By that average weight, weight variation and percentage weight variation is also calculated. This procedure of uniformity was followed from I.P.

Hardness test:

Hardness of tablet is defined as the force applied across the diameter of the tablet in the order to break the tablet. Hardness test is very much essential for tablet. It helps to know the ability of the tablet to withstand the different mechanical stresses on the tablet and different storage conditions. The chipping, abrasion and breakage of tablet during storage and handling conditions depend on hardness of the tablet.

Friability test:

It is the test for the measurement of mechanical strength of the tablet. Roche-friabilator is used for conducting the friability tests for tablets. First a batch of tablets was taken and is weighed and then they are subjected to friability test. The equipment consists of friability chamber in which pre-weighed tablets are placed at a distance of 6 inch from each and chamber is rotated with 25rpm speed and the time is set for about 4 minutes. Then after completing its rotation then the tablets are removed and again weighed. There will be a loss of weight observed.

Disintegration and dissolution test:

In this test the time required for the drug to undergo dissolution and disintegration is known. It is performed in the disintegration apparatus. Generally distilled water is taken as the medium to disintegrate the drug. The distilled water should be at nearly about 37°C and the time in seconds is taken as the disintegration time.

Wetting time and water absorption ratio:

In this test the tablet is placed in five circular tissue papers and then it is placed in the Petridis. Then water (10 ml) containing methylene blue (0.1% w/v) was added in to the Petridis. Then time taken by the dye to reach the tablet was observed. Water absorption ratio can be calculated using -Water absorption ratio = $(W_a - W_b) / W_b$, Where W_b = weight of tablet before absorption of water and W_a = weight of tablet after absorption of water.

In-vitro dispersion time:

In this test the tablet is dropped in a Sorenson's buffer whose ph is 6.8. It can also be tested with salivary fluid.

Stability studies for fast dissolving tablets:

These fast dissolving tablets were studied and tested for stability at 40C and 75% RH condition for period of three months. Then tablets were wrapped in aluminum foil and packed in black PVC bottle and specific humidity conditions are maintained in the chamber for 3 months. Then they were tested for the hardness, disintegration time and in vitro drug release study.

Dryness test/tack test:

Tack test is the test performed for the evaluation of fast dissolving films. It can be described as the tenacity with which the strip adheres to an accessory that has been pressed into contact with the strip. This gives the dryness value of the substance.

Tensile strength:

It helps to evaluate the strength of the films under stress conditions. Tensile strength is the maximum stress applied on the substance at a point until the strip specimen breaks. It is calculated by the applied load at rupture divided by the cross-sectional area of the strip. Generally the elongation increases with increase in concentrations of plasticizer.

$$\text{Tensile strength} = \text{Ratio of Increase in length of the strip to initial length of the strip} \times 100.$$

Percent elongation:

Due to application of stress on the sample, a strip sample stretches and this is referred to as strain. Strain is basically the deformation of strip divided by original dimension of the sample. Generally elongation of strip increases with increase in concentration of the plasticizer.

$$\% \text{ Elongation} = \text{Ratio of increase in length of strip to initial length of strip} \times 100.$$

Tear resistance:

Tear resistance helps to evaluate the tearing strength of the fast dissolving film. Tear resistance is the ability of a material to withstand the mechanical stresses of tearing. Generally very low rate of loading 51mm (2 in)/min is employed to measure the force to initiate tearing. The maximum stress or force required to tear the material is recorded as the tear resistance value in newton's (or pounds-force).

Young's modulus:

Young's modulus is the capacity of a material to withstand the mechanical stresses which results in changes in length. It can also be referred as modulus of elasticity. It is represented as the ratio of applied stress over strain in the region of elastic deformation.

Folding endurance:

Folding endurance is the evaluation test done for the fast dissolving film. It can be defined as the measure of durability of film when it is folded for several times until it breaks. The folding endurance value can be given by number of times the film is folded without breaking.

Swelling property:

In this test the film is weighed before and is placed in a pre-weighed stainless steel wire mesh. Film swelling study is conducted using simulated saliva solution. The mesh containing film sample is submerged into 15ml medium in a plastic container. Increase in the weight of the film is observed at preset time interval until a constant weight is attained. The degree of swelling is calculated using

Formula: - $\alpha = (wt - wo)/wo$, wt is weight of film at time t, and wo is weight of film at time zero.

Transparency:

The transparency of the films can be determined using a simple UV spectrophotometer. Samples are cut into rectangles and placed on the internal side of the spectrophotometer cell. Transmittance of films at 600 nm is determined. The transparency of the films can be calculated as-

$$\text{Transparency} = (\log T_{600})/b = - \epsilon c$$

where T600 is the transmittance at 600 nm, b is the film thickness (mm) and c is concentration.

Contact angle:

The contact angle is a quantitative measure of the wettability of the surface, represented by the angle at which a liquid or vapor interface makes with a solid surface. Contact angle measurements are performed at the room temperature with a goniometry. A drop of double distilled water was placed on the surface of the dry film. Images of the water droplet were recorded for 10 seconds by means of digital camera; digital images are analyzed by the image 1.28v software for angle determination.

Moisture content:

In this test the film is pre-weighed and placed in desiccators for about 24 hours. Then after that it is removed and again weighed and the differences between the weights are calculated to know the moisture content. It can be calculated by ratio of difference in initial and final weight to the initial weight and multiplied with 100.

Table-1: A few Marketed Dosage Forms:

Brand name	Active ingredient	Class of drug
Zofran ODT	Ondansetron	Stimulants
Abilify Discmelt	Aripiprazole	Aripiprazole
Felden fast melt	Piroxicam	Opioid
Nimulid MD	Nimusulide	Anti-pyretic
Benadryl	Diphenhydramine HCl	Expectorant
Allegra ODT	Fexofenadine	Antihistamines
Febrectol	Paracetamol	NSAID
Adzenys XR-ODT	Amphetamine	Acetylcholinesterase inhibitors
Kemstro	Baclofen	NSAID
Zotacet MD	Cetirizine Hcl	Anti-histaminic

CONCLUSION

Fast dissolving dosage forms have several advantages over the other drugs. It has a great patient compliance. It has several advantages like fast disintegration, fast dissolution. It gives quick onset of action and also improves bio-availability. It shows its action within the 60 seconds of administration of the drug in oral cavity. It is helpful for the people who are mentally ill, geriatric and pediatric patients and the people suffering from allergic reactions. The stability and efficacy of the drug is also high. Fast dissolving dosage forms has a good demand in the market as it has several advantages then compared to the other dosage forms. Even fast dissolving films have several benefits over the fast dissolving tablets. This is the emerging technology growing fast in the pharmaceutical industry as there is a rise in demand.

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